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APPLICATION OF FOREIGN LAW IN TURKISH COURTS**

Abstract: Turkish courts do not exclusively apply Turkish law. In other words, foreign law may be applied to private law transactions and relations involving a foreign element due to the conflict of laws rules. According to Article 2 of the Turkish Code on Private International and Civil Procedure Law numbered 5718, the judge shall *ex officio* apply the rules of Turkish conflict of laws and competent foreign law under these rules. However, the different treatment of foreign law as fact or law in various legal orders changes the consequences of the application of foreign law. As a rule, the judge knows and applies the law in accordance with the principle of *iura novit curia*. However, in cases where foreign law is applied, the judge cannot be expected to be familiar with every legal system other than their own. This paper aims to explain how to determine the content of foreign law and how to apply it in cases where foreign law is applied in Turkish courts.

Keywords: application of foreign law, law, fact, *iura novit curia*.

1. Introduction

The globalising world has increased relations with foreign elements. Moreover, mass migration flows cause individuals to settle in a country other than their country of nationality or residence. This situation may lead to the application of foreign law, especially in personal and family law matters and transactions of the persons in question. Turkey has experienced many influxes due to its geographical location. The unexpected increase in the number of foreigners in Turkey has caused Turkish judges to encounter cases involving foreign elements.

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In private law disputes with a foreign element, the judge determines the applicable law through the conflict of laws rules. This determination either refers to Turkish law or to the law of foreign jurisdictions. The judge undoubtedly knows and applies their own law. In other words, in cases where the applicable law is determined as Turkish law, the Turkish judge will easily apply this law since the judge knows Turkish law. However, when the applicable law points to the law of a foreign country, the Turkish judge undergoes the problem of how to apply this law.

According to Article 2 of the Turkish Code on Private International and Civil Procedure Law numbered 5718, the judge shall *ex officio* apply the rules of Turkish conflict of laws and competent foreign law under these rules. Therefore, neither party to the case has the burden of proving the law applicable to the dispute involving a foreign element. Not expected to know the foreign law, the judge may seek the assistance of the parties regarding the content of the foreign law. However, this assistance cannot be characterised as burden of proof.

Moreover, The European Convention on Information on Foreign Law was signed in 1968 to facilitate judges' knowledge of the content of foreign law. Turkey is also a party to this convention. Pursuant to Article 1 of this convention the Contracting Parties undertake to supply one another, in accordance with the provisions of the present Convention, with information on their law and procedure in civil and commercial fields as well as on their judicial organisation.

The acceptance of foreign law as *law* or as *fact* leads to different legal consequences. In some legal orders such as Turkey and Switzerland, foreign law is applied as law. When foreign law is considered as law, the determination of the content of the foreign law is not imposed on the parties. However, in cases where foreign law is accepted as fact, the burden of proving the facts is placed on the parties.

This study aims to outline Turkish perspective on the determination of the content of foreign law in cases where foreign law is applied. The role of the judge and the parties in this determination is also within the scope of this study. In this context, the application of the conflict of laws rules, the application of the foreign law determined as a result of the application of these conflict of laws rules and finally the determination of the content of the foreign law will be discussed in the light of Turkish courts' decisions.

2. The Application of the Conflict of Laws Rules

In the continental European legal system, cross-border disputes are resolved by means of Savigny's method. In this method, various categories of law are linked to the legal order of a particular country through the medium of connecting factors.¹ In other words, conflict of laws rules are localisation-based rules that ensure the application of the law most closely related to the dispute.

The application of conflict of laws rules differs between legal systems. In this context, three systems can be mentioned². According to the first system adopted in the Anglo-American legal system, the conflict of laws rules are propounded by the parties.³ In other words, the judge does not *ex officio* consider the conflict of laws rules, but expects for the parties to plead them. In this system, conflict of laws rules cannot be applied by the judge unless invoked by at least one of the parties.⁴ When a party propounds foreign law, that party can make the application of conflict rules compulsory and binding, and it becomes the duty of the judge to determine the content of those conflict rules.⁵

According to the second system the judge applies the conflict of laws rules by its own motion. This system is recognised in the countries of continental Europe. If the dispute before the court has a foreign element, the judge *ex officio* applies the conflict of laws as they apply domestic law rules.⁶ Irrespective of their source, whether stemming from domestic legislation, international treaties, or EU regulations, the conflict rules are an integral component of the domestic legal systems within these countries.⁷

Finally, a mixed system is applied in France, Sweden and Finland.⁸ In French law, the application of conflict of laws rules is not regulated by an explicit statutory provision, but instead it is clarified by the case law of the

¹ Nishitani, Y., *Treatment of Foreign Law-Dynamics Towards Convergence? - General Report*, Treatment of Foreign Law- Dynamics Towards Convergence? (Ed. Y. Nishitani), Switzerland: Springer, 2017, p. 7.

² Özel, S., Erkan M., Pürselim H. S., Karaca H. A., *Milletlerarası özel Hukuk (Private International Law)*, İstanbul: On iki Levha, 2nd Ed., 2023, p. 150.

³ Yöney, C., *Yabancı Hukukun Uygulanması (Application of Foreign Law)*, İstanbul: On İki Levha, 2018, p. 24.

⁴ Nishitani, *op. cit.*, p. 15.

⁵ Nishitani, *ibid.*, 15.

⁶ Nishitani, *ibid.*, p. 12.

⁷ Nishitani, *ibid.*, p. 12.

⁸ Yöney, *op. cit.*, p. 31-32.

French Supreme Court (*Cour de Cassation*).⁹ According to this jurisprudence, the application of the conflict of laws rules is determined depending on the nature of the subject matter of the dispute.¹⁰ If the dispute is related to a right that can be freely disposed of (*droit disponible*) conflict of laws rules are generally applied at the invocation of the parties.¹¹ However, the judge has the discretion to apply the conflict of laws rules when deemed necessary.¹² On the other hand, if the subject matter of the dispute relates to a right that cannot be freely disposed of (*droit indisponible*), then the judge is required to *ex officio* apply the conflicts of law rules.¹³ The rights that cannot be freely disposed of in this context relate to matters of personal status and family law.¹⁴ Conversely, rights pertaining to areas such as commercial and civil contracts, non-contractual obligations, successions, or the legal status of a company are deemed to be freely disposed of.¹⁵

The system in continental European countries has been adopted in Turkish law. Article 2 of Private International Law and Procedural Law¹⁶ (hereinafter PILA) deals with the application of foreign law. Article 2 states: “The judge shall *ex officio* apply the Turkish conflict of law rules and the applicable foreign law pursuant to these rules.”¹⁷ As Turkish private international law rules are mandatory, Turkish courts naturally apply these rules as a matter of official duty.¹⁸ However, unlike the conflict of laws rules, the foreign element and the connecting factors shall be proved by the party claiming it.¹⁹ Pursuant to article 25 of Civil Procedural Code²⁰ except for the exceptions provided by law, the judge may not automatically consider what has not been said by either party or the facts, and may not even act in such

⁹ Corneloup, S., *France – The Evolving Balance Between the Judge and the Parties in France, Treatment of Foreign Law - Dynamics towards Convergence?*, (Ed. Y. Nishitani), Switzerland: Springer, p. 158.

¹⁰ Corneloup, *ibid.*, p. 159.

¹¹ Corneloup, *ibid.*, p. 159.

¹² Nishitani, p. 13.

¹³ Corneloup, *op. cit.*, p. 159.

¹⁴ Corneloup, *ibid.*, p. 160.

¹⁵ Corneloup, *ibid.*, p. 161.

¹⁶ Law no. 5718 and dated 27.11.2007 (*Official Gazette*. 12.12.2007-26728).

¹⁷ Tarman, Z. D., *Turkey: The Treatment of Foreign Law in Turkey, Treatment of Foreign Law - Dynamics towards Convergence?*, (Ed. Y. Nishitani), Switzerland: Springer, p. 552.

¹⁸ Tarman, *ibid.*, p. 552.

¹⁹ Özel, *op. cit.*, p. 151.

²⁰ Law no. 6100 and dated 12.01.2011 (*Official Gazette*. 04.02.2011-27836).

a way as to remind them. Except in cases specified by law, the judge may not gather evidence spontaneously. Therefore, whether the necessary facts for the application of the conflict of laws rules have been established depends on the evidence provided by the parties.

3. 3. Application of the Foreign Law to Which the Conflict of Laws Rules Refer

Conflict of laws rules resolve the dispute by localising it to a particular legal order. In other words, conflict of laws rules are indicative rules.²¹ Therefore, the treatment of foreign law indicated by the conflict of laws rules may have different legal consequences in terms of procedural law. There are different opinions and practices regarding the nature of foreign law.²² In the systems where foreign law is accepted as “*fact*”, foreign law is treated as fact that must be proven by the parties to the case.²³ Foreign law must be sufficiently pleaded and substantiated by the parties to enable the judge to apply it.²⁴ This system imposes an active role on the parties in ascertaining the foreign law. The reason for the application of foreign law as fact in the Anglo-American legal system is the idea that the judge can only apply the domestic law in their country as law.²⁵

If the foreign law is accepted as “*law*”, the foreign law to be applied shall be applied *suo moto* by the local judge.²⁶ In other words, foreign law is no different from local law in terms of application. This approach equates foreign law with *lex fori*.²⁷ In cases where foreign law must be applied, it is considered to be the “official duty” of the judge to make the necessary determination and apply the law determined. This is the approach adopted in the continental European legal system.

In Turkish private international law, foreign law is applied as “*law*”. In other words, both the conflict of laws rules and the foreign law indicated by

²¹ Şanlı, C., Esen, E., Figanmeşe-Ataman, İ., *Milletlerarası Özel Hukuk (Private International Law)*, İstanbul: Beta, 10th Ed., 2023, p. 6.

²² Yaşar, T. N., *Türk Mahkemelerinde Yabancı Hukukun Uygulanması, (Application of Foreign Law in the Courts of Turkey)*, Public and Private International Law Bulletin, 33 (2), 2016, p. 79; Erkan, M., *Türk Milletlerarası Özel Hukuk Sisteminde Yabancı Hukukun Tatbiki: Olan vs. Olması Gereken*, Milletlerarası Özel Hukukta Güncel Konular Sempozyumu (Eds: B. Tiryakioğlu, M. Aygün, and al.), Eskişehir, 21-22 April 2016, p. 518.

²³ Nishitani, *op. cit.*, p. 18.

²⁴ Nishitani, *ibid.* p. 18.

²⁵ Erkan, *op. cit.*, p. 519.

²⁶ Erkan, *ibid.*, p. 518.

²⁷ Özel and al, *op. cit.*, p. 154.

these rules should be applied *ex officio* in the courts. Foreign law derives its application authority from the PILA. Nonetheless, the legitimacy of foreign law originates from the legal system to which it belongs. Since judges apply foreign law *ex officio*, they are not bound by the information and documents submitted by the parties.

4. Ascertainment of Foreign Law

4.1. In General

Since the foreign law indicated by the conflict of laws rules is applied *ex officio*, the problem of how to determine the content of this law comes to the fore. In Turkish substantive law, it is essential that the judge knows the law. According to the Civil Procedural Code of Turkey (art. 33), the judge knows the law and applies it *ex officio*. This fundamental principle (*iura novit curia*) in substantive law is not anticipated to be applicable to foreign law.²⁸ Therefore, the determination of the content of the foreign law unfamiliar to the judge should be subject to a special procedure.²⁹

In accordance with the PILA, a judge is permitted to seek the parties' cooperation in ascertaining the substance of foreign law. However, since the judge will apply the foreign law *ex officio*, this assistance is not a duty imposed on the parties.³⁰ In the initial stage, the primary emphasis is placed on establishing the content of foreign law based on the judge's individual legal knowledge and their independent research.³¹ Furthermore, the judge is required to apply the foreign law in the manner that it is practiced in the corresponding foreign jurisdiction.³²

4.2. Conventions

The aim of the judge is to access accurate and sufficient information so as to resolve the dispute.³³ Judges use different methods to determine the pertinent articles of foreign law. In this context, the judge may obtain information on the applicable law from the relevant countries within the scope of bilateral and multilateral legal aid agreements to which the Republic of Tur-

²⁸ Şanlı and al., *op. cit.*, p. 75.

²⁹ Şanlı and al., *ibid.*, p. 75.

³⁰ Şanlı and al., *ibid.*, p. 75.

³¹ Tarman, *op. cit.*, p. 556.

³² Tarman, *ibid.*, p. 556.

³³ Tarman, *ibid.*, p. 556.

key is a party. Turkey³⁴ acceded to the *European Convention on Information on Foreign Law*,³⁵ commonly referred to as the ‘London Convention,’ which was signed in London under the Council of Europe’s guidance.³⁶ This accession was aimed at simplifying and expediting the process of acquiring information about foreign law. Article 2 of the Convention mandates that every Contracting Party establish or designate a receiving agency responsible for executing the tasks specified in the Convention’s provisions. The receiving and transmitting agency of Turkey is the Ministry of Justice. This convention has been referred to in many judgements of the Court of Cassation.³⁷ However, the information received in this context is limited and consists only of the translation of the relevant legislation.³⁸ Therefore, it is not sufficient to resolve the dispute. The fact that the legal legislation is not translated by lawyers causes semantic confusion.³⁹

4.3. Other Sources

The Ministry of Justice, Turkish embassies and consulates abroad, and foreign delegations in Turkey are potential sources of assistance for the judge.⁴⁰ One of the methods used by the courts is to seek assistance from law faculties and/or court experts.⁴¹ However, this system is not sufficient to resolve the dispute. In fact, faculty members provide translations of the relevant legislation.⁴² This translation does not provide sufficient information about the foreign law that should be applied as *law*. In other words, foreign

³⁴ *Official Gazette*. 26.8.1975-15338. Turkey is a signatory to the supplementary protocol of the convention as well (*Official Gazette*. 14.4.2004-25433).

³⁵ <https://rm.coe.int/1680072314> (accessed 8.11.2023), European Treaty Series No. 62.

³⁶ Tarman, *op. cit.*, p. 558; Tunçağıl, G. G., *MÖHUK Kapsamında Yabancı Hukukun Muhtevasının Tespitine İlişkin Hükümün Dğerlendirilmesi ve Bazı Hukuk Düzenleri ile Karşılaştırılması*, MÖHUK’ta Reform (Eds. S. Özel, M. Erkan, H. S. Pürselim), İstanbul: On İki Levha, 2023, p. 157; Erkan, M., Yöney, C., *MÖHUK Hayatta mı, Can mı Çekiyor?*, MÖHUK’ta Reform (Eds. S. Özel, M. Erkan, H. S. Pürselim), İstanbul: On İki Levha, 2023, p.59.

³⁷ Civil Department (No: 2) of Court of Cassation E.2006/16427, K.2007/5497, T. 3.4.2007; Civil Department (No: 2) of Court of Cassation E. 2009/3562, K. 2009/7289, T. 15.4.2009 (www.yargitay.gov.tr).

³⁸ Erkan, *op. cit.*, p. 522.

³⁹ Erkan, *ibid.*, p. 552.

⁴⁰ Tarman, *op. cit.*, p. 559.

⁴¹ Arslan, İ., *Yabancı Unsurlu Özel Hukuk Uyuşmazlıklarında Yabancı Hukukun İçeriği Hakkında Bilgi Edinilmesinde Bilirkişinin Rolü*, (*The Role of Expert Witness in Obtaining Information on the Content of Foreign Law in Private International Law Cases*), TAAD, 13(51), July 2022, p. 324.

⁴² However, for detailed information on the fact that in practice, legal experts in this field are not well funded, see Erkan and Yöney, *op. cit.*, p. 76.

law must be understood and applied in accordance with its meaning, nature, scope and interpretation in the country to which it belongs.⁴³

5. Inability To Ascertain Foreign Law

According to the article 2 of PILA, if the provisions of the foreign law relevant to the dispute cannot be determined despite all investigations, Turkish law shall apply. However, if the judge directly applies Turkish law without any research on foreign law, the Court of Cassation will reverse the decision of the court of first instance as the foreign law is treated as *law*.⁴⁴ As a matter of fact, according to Article 371(1)(a) of the Civil Procedural Code, non-application or misapplication of the law is a ground for reversal.

6. Current Problems Faced By Courts

Determining the content of foreign law can take a very long time. The inability to ascertain foreign law within a reasonable timeframe can result in the trial not proceeding in a timely manner, potentially leading to a violation of the right to a trial within a reasonable period.⁴⁵ In the case of *Karalyos And Huber v. Hungary And Greece*⁴⁶ of the European Court of Human Rights

⁴³ Erkan, *op. cit.*, p. 523; Tanrıbilir, F. B., *5718 Sayılı Milletlerarası Özel Hukuk ve Usul Hukuku Hakkında Kanunun Uygulmasına Dair Sorunlar ve Öneriler*, MÖHUK'ta Reform (Eds. S. Özel, M. Erkan, H. S. Pürselim), İstanbul: On İki Levha, 2023, p. 12.

⁴⁴ See Civil Department (No:11) of Court of Cassation E. 2019/1537, K. 2019/3206, T.29.04.2019; Civil Department (No:18) of Court of Cassation E. 2005/2899-K. 2005/4027, T. 21.4.2005: Şanlı and al., *op. cit.*, p.68, footnote 113.

⁴⁵ Arslan, İ., *Yabancı Unsurlu Özel Hukuk Uyuşmazlıklarında Makul Sürede Yargılanma Hakkı İle Yabancı Hukukun İçeriğinin Temin Edilmesi Arasındaki İlişki (The Relationship Between The Right To A Fair Trial Within A Reasonable Time And Ascertainment Of Content Of Foreign Applicable Law In Private International Law Cases)*, Public and Private International Law Bulletin, 37(2), 2017, p. 60.

⁴⁶ Application no. 75116/01, 6.7.2004, <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/>, accessed 9.11.2023. The lawsuit revolved around a civil claim in Hungary seeking compensation for the losses suffered by two Hungarian individuals due to a fire aboard a ship belonging to a Greek corporation. The Court determined that the duration of the legal proceedings was unduly prolonged, partly attributed to the uncooperative stance of the Greek authorities. They neglected to provide essential information regarding pertinent Greek legislation to the Hungarian court. The Court, concluding that the majority of the delays were attributable to the actions of the Hungarian state, ruled that Hungary had breached Article 6 of the European Convention on Human Rights. Nine years after the claim was filed, the details of the foreign applicable law had yet to be determined, and the legal proceedings were still in their initial stages before the Hungarian courts. For detailed information on the case, see, Den Heijer, M., *Shared Responsibility Before The European Court of Human Rights*, Netherlands International Law

(*ECtHR*), two criteria were taken into consideration in determining the “reasonable period”. These are the behaviour of the judicial and administrative authorities participating in the activity of determining the content of foreign law and the importance for the parties of completing the proceedings within a reasonable time.

Another problem faced by Turkish judges is the personal status and family law cases of Syrians. Syrians living in Turkey have temporary protection status. In Article 91 of Law (No:6458) on Foreigners and International Protection; Temporary Protection is defined as the following⁴⁷:

“Temporary protection may be provided for foreigners who have been forced to leave their country, cannot return to the country that they have left, and have arrived at or crossed the borders of Turkey in a mass influx situation seeking immediate and temporary protection.”

Syrians are not recognised as *refugees* because Turkey has restricted the application of the 1951 Refugee Convention (Geneva Convention) to individuals who have become refugees as a result of events that took place in Europe. Turkish judges have difficulties in obtaining information on Syrian law, especially in cases concerning the personal status of Syrians and family law matters. Article 4 of the PILA stipulates that for *refugees*, the habitual residence shall be considered when nationality is accepted as the connecting factor. In some court decisions, Syrians have been recognised under this article even though they are not refugees⁴⁸. In some judgements, the judge applied Turkish law on the grounds that they could not obtain information about foreign law despite all efforts due to the internal disorder in Syria.⁴⁹ In some court decisions, it is stated that the request for ascertaining the foreign law is forwarded to the Ministry of Justice and that it is not possible for the Ministry to meet this request.⁵⁰

Yet another issue that needs to be underlined is the Turkish employees sent to foreign countries to work. Therefore, problems arise in obtaining

Review, 60(3), 2013, p. 423.

⁴⁷ Temporary Protection in Türkiye, en.goc.gov.tr, accessed 8.11.2023.

⁴⁸ Gaziantep Regional Courts of Justice, Civil Department (No: 2) E. 2017/1082; K. 2017/1014, T. 19.7.2017.

⁴⁹ Adana Regional Courts of Justice, Civil Department (No: 2) E. 2019/1641; K. 2021/894, T. 1.6.2021. *“Due to the state of war in Syria and the inability to determine the applicable law, the application of Turkish law in the case is in accordance with the procedure and the law”*.

⁵⁰ Gaziantep Regional Courts of Justice, Civil Department (No: 2) E.2019/2107; K. 2019/2201, T. 23.12.2019, *“The Ministry of Justice, Directorate General for Foreign Relations and European Union Affairs responded to the request for the Civil Code of the Syrian Arab Republic, in particular its provisions on paternity, by stating that it was not possible to fulfil the request at this stage”*.

the law of these developing countries where Turkish companies invest. In a judgment rendered by Ankara Regional Courts of Justice (No: 30),⁵¹ it was ruled that an expert in the labour law of Papua New Guinea, the employee's habitual place of work, should be consulted.

7. Conclusion

Since the determination of foreign law is a time-consuming, difficult and costly task, judges tend to resolve the dispute by applying *lex fori*. In order to ensure the justice of private international law, the law most closely connected with the dispute should be applied. Obtaining foreign law only as a translation of the text of the law often leads to misapplication of foreign law. Although efforts are being made to ensure the flow of information between the legal systems of the member states of the European Union,⁵² this issue should be addressed *globally*.

In the member states of the European Union, the flow of information can be easy. However, Turkey's location and the mass influx of asylum seekers necessitates the application of different legal systems in Turkish courts. Facilitating access to foreign law for parties and judges will be an incentive for the application of foreign law.⁵³ The use of foreign experts and lawyers as court experts may also prevent this problem.⁵⁴ In this context, developments in technology and artificial intelligence can also be used to prevent language dependency. However, all initiatives to be taken for the establishment of private international law justice should have a global dimension.

Summary

The application of conflict of laws rules differs between legal systems. In the Anglo-American legal system, conflict of laws rules must be asserted by the parties. In the continental European legal system, the judge applies the conflict of laws rules *suo moto*, without the parties having to raise them. According to the mixed system adopted by France, the application of the con-

⁵¹ E. 2023/2643, K. 2023/3511, T. 21.09.2023. For a decision decreeing the need to obtain information about the law of Gabon and Iraq, see. Ankara Regional Courts of Justice (No. 30), E. 2023/2453, K. 2023/2804, T. 6.7.2023.

⁵² European Judicial Network (EJN) serves as a connected group of representatives from various nations, working together to enhance collaboration in the field of criminal justice. <https://www.ejn-crimjust.europa.eu/ejn2021/ContentDetail/EN/2/63>, (accessed 9.11.2023).

⁵³ Erkan, *op. cit.*, p. 528.

⁵⁴ Erkan, *ibid.*, p. 528.

flict of laws rules is determined depending on the nature of the subject matter of the dispute. In Turkish law, the judge applies the foreign law *ex officio*.

Given that conflict of laws rules require the application of foreign law *suo moto*, the issue of determining the content of this law becomes prominent. Judges employ various methods to ascertain the relevant provisions of foreign law. They may acquire information on the applicable law from the respective countries through bilateral and multilateral legal assistance agreements in which the Republic of Turkey participates. Turkey ratified the European Convention on Information on Foreign Law. There are various ways of obtaining information about the content of foreign law outside of the Convention. The judge could seek support from the Ministry of Justice, Turkish diplomatic missions overseas, and international delegations within Turkey. Moreover, the judge may also consult law faculties or court experts. However, foreign law needs to be comprehended and implemented in line with its significance, characteristics, extent, and interpretation within its originating nation. If the provisions of the foreign law relevant to the dispute cannot be determined despite all investigations, Turkish law shall apply.

Determining the substance of foreign law can be a time-consuming process. Therefore, judges tend to apply the *lex fori*. This situation is detrimental to the justice of private international law. A global step must be taken to achieve this justice.

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